

Implementation And Evaluation of Information System for The Integration of Distributor Turnover Calculation

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ABSTRACT

Management information systems are very important in a company. Several companies face challenges in integrating information systems that result in inefficient manual processes, the risk of data input errors, and delays in the strategic decision-making process. This paper aims to analyze the impact of information system implementation in improving the accuracy of distributor turnover calculations. The method used involves collecting data from various departments involved in processing distributor turnover data, analyzing existing systems, and evaluating performance after implementing the new system. The implementation of an integrated information system can reduce turnover calculation errors, accelerate data reconciliation processes, improve operational efficiency, support data analysis, increase transparency in reporting, and optimize business processes while being a strategic step in supporting long-term business growth.

Keywords: Management Information Systems, Financial Information Systems, ERP, Digital Transformation

INTRODUCTION

Information technology has become an integral part of business operations. Companies across industries increasingly rely on integrated information systems to manage data, improve operational efficiency, and accelerate decision-making. Digital transformation is no longer just an option, but a necessity for businesses to remain competitive and adapt to changing market dynamics. Management Information Systems (MIS) play an important role in helping companies manage and analyze data more effectively, including in aspects of finance, production, distribution, and customer relations. With an integrated information system, companies can avoid delays, recording errors, and inefficiencies that often occur in business processes that are still manual or fragmented between departments.

Manufacturing companies that have extensive distribution networks face challenges in managing sales data and turnover from various distributors as a crucial issue. In practice, the process of calculating distributor turnover is often done manually or using separate systems in each branch or region. This causes the potential for data inconsistency, reporting delays, and

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the risk of duplication or calculation errors that often make management face obstacles in obtaining accurate real-time data and can affect the company's strategic decision-making. According to Chugh et al. (2017); Chofreh et al. (2018); El Farmawi et al. (2019) Enterprise resource planning (ERP) is a development of Manufacture Resource Planning II (MRP II) which is also an evolution of the previously developed Material Requirement Planning. Shkurti et al. (2021); Saade et al. (2016) in Indonesia, Enterprise Resource Planning itself has been widely used in companies with high complexity. PT. XXX, as one of the leading manufacturing companies in Indonesia with an extensive distribution network, faces challenges in calculating distributor turnover that has not been integrated. Differences in calculation methods between cash and credit payment distributors often cause delays in turnover recapitulation and increase the risk of errors due to manual recording in various departments. The lack of system integration has the potential to hamper data accuracy and operational efficiency, especially in financial reporting. Therefore, an integrated information system implementation is needed to align the turnover calculation process, improve data accuracy, accelerate reporting, and support more effective decision making. This paper aims to discuss and analyze the obstacles faced by PT. XXX in calculating distributor turnover due to the lack of integration of information systems between departments and to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of the information system currently used in supporting the turnover calculation process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information Technology and Information Systems

Information Technology (IT) has become a major pillar in supporting operations and decision-making in various business sectors. IT plays a crucial role in processing, storing, and distributing relevant information to related parties. One of the most important IT implementations in the business world is the Management Information System (MIS). MIS is a system designed to collect, manage, and present data so that it can be processed into useful information for management. The role of MIS in a company is able to increase operational efficiency, minimize manual errors, and accelerate the flow of information needed. The Financial Information System is one part of the Management Information System that focuses on managing the company's financial data. This system functions to record, manage, and report financial transactions, making it easier for companies to conduct financial analysis, budget planning, and accurate financial reporting. With the Financial Information System, companies can increase accuracy and transparency in their financial management. This is important, especially for companies that face complex challenges in managing cash flow, accounts receivable, and tax reporting.

The information system operates based on the flow of input, process, output, which functions to manage data systematically to support operations and decision-making in the company. The input stage is the process of entering data into the system, including sales transactions, customer information, and inventory reports, which are the basis for information processing. At the process stage, the data that has been entered is processed using certain algorithms or

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business rules, such as distributor turnover calculations, stock analysis, or payment matching to ensure accuracy and efficiency in data management. The results of this process are then presented in the form of output, such as financial reports, turnover summaries, or analytical dashboards that provide a comprehensive picture for management in making strategic decisions.

Enterprise Resource Planning

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) is an integrated system that functions to manage and coordinate various business processes in one centralized platform. ERP integrates key functions in a company, such as accounting, finance, human resources, logistics, and manufacturing, into one interconnected system. Companies that implement ERP can improve inter-departmental collaboration, reduce data duplication, and create more efficient workflows. According to Al-Zoubi et al. (2018); Altamony et al. (2016) Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) is a computer-based integrated system designed to process company transactions and facilitate integrated and real-time planning, production, and consumer response. This allows management to monitor business performance and identify emerging problems or opportunities quickly. ERP also helps companies improve data accuracy, accelerate business processes, and ensure compliance with applicable regulations.

THE INTEGRATION OF DISTRIBUTOR TURNOVER CALCULATION

Company Profile

As one of the leading and respected corporate groups in Indonesia, Group XXX is currently a large company with 23,000 employees spread across five industrial and factory locations in East Java and Cibitung, Jakarta. Starting from a kitchen equipment manufacturer in 1967, Group XXX has now developed its business into eight business groups: Consumer Products, Consumer Industrial Products, Construction and Building Materials, Hospitality, Commercial Property and Industrial Estates, Banking, Trading and Distribution, Infrastructure and Energy, and Miscellaneous Businesses. In addition to developing its own companies, Group XXX has also attracted a number of multinational companies to become joint venture partners.

Driven by a strong entrepreneurial spirit, Mr. Alim Husin, the founder, has realized his vision to make XXX Group a leading business group in Indonesia. With the support of his sons, first his eldest son, Alim Markus, then followed by his three other sons, Alim Mulia Sastra, Alim Satria, and Alim Prakasa. A number of independent executives also dedicate their efforts to the success of XXX Group. Through the dedication and hard work of all its employees, XXX Group continues to improve reliable economic performance that ensures sustainable improvement of shareholder values and its contribution to Indonesia's economic development.

PT. XXX Activities

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To give appreciation to distributors who have achieved the highest sales performance, every year PT. XXX holds an event titled BEST OF THE BEST. This event aims to give awards to five distributors with the highest turnover from all divisions, including household appliances, electronics, plastics, and metals. This event is not only a form of appreciation, but also as motivation for distributors to continue to improve their sales performance in the following years. During the implementation of the BEST OF THE BEST event, there was an incident that caused chaos during the event. The error occurred due to inaccuracy in the calculation of distributor turnover carried out by the accounting department. The results of the turnover recapitulation announced during the event were different from the actual final calculation, triggering confusion and dissatisfaction from the distributors who attended, because the awards given did not accurately reflect their turnover. This incident provided an important lesson for PT. XXX that the accuracy and precision of data in calculating turnover is very crucial, especially for an event as big as BEST OF THE BEST, which involves distributors from various regions.

System Implementation at PT. XXX

The system used by PT. XXX is still fragmented in each department, silos cause inefficiencies in data management and coordination between units. The marketing department receives and processes orders using a separate system that is not directly connected to other departments. The factory manages the delivery of goods using a different system, which is not automatically synchronized with the marketing department's ordering system. The accounting department receives and records financial data through a separate system, where the data sources used are also different, especially in recording distributor turnover. The difference occurs because PT. XXX has two types of distributors, namely distributors with cash payments where the turnover is calculated based on the initial payment before the goods are sent, and distributors with credit payments whose turnover is calculated based on payments for goods that have been sent previously.

The process of using a cash Delivery Order (DO) at PT. XXX begins with the entry of an order from a customer to the marketing team. After receiving the order, the marketing team then issues a Purchase Order (PO) and sends it to the order maker. The order maker's job is to process the PO by creating a DO according to the agreed order. After the DO is completed, the document is returned to the marketing team to be billed to the customer. In the cash DO payment mechanism, the customer will make the payment using a giro. After the giro is received by the marketing team, the document is then submitted to the cashier for validation. This validation aims to ensure that the payment received is in accordance with the amount stated in the DO and that there are no errors in the transaction process. After the cashier completes the validation process, the marketing team authorizes the factory so that the order can be processed further. With this authorization, the factory will begin planning the delivery of goods according to the DO that has been previously validated.

The process of using a credit Delivery Order (DO) at PT. XXX begins with the entry of an order from a customer to the marketing team. After receiving the order, the marketing team

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issues a Purchase Order (PO) and sends it to the order maker. The order maker then creates a DO based on the PO received, ensuring that all order details are in accordance with the customer's request. After the DO is completed, the document is returned to the marketing team for authorization to the factory. This authorization is an important step before the goods are processed and sent to the customer. After receiving authorization, the factory will carry out the shipping planning according to the approved DO. Unlike the cash DO system, in the credit DO system, the billing process is carried out based on the delivery note issued after the goods are shipped. This delivery note is official proof that the goods have been sent to the customer, which will later be used as a basis for the billing process by the finance or accounting team. With this system, customers can make payments according to the due date agreed upon in their credit agreement. The lack of integration of this system causes inconsistencies in data recording between departments, increases the potential for duplication of information, and slows down the process of calculating the company's turnover and financial reporting, which can ultimately impact overall operational efficiency.

Lack of Integration

According to Chofreh et al. (2018); El Farmawi et al. (2019) the problem often faced by companies is how to organize and integrate their existing data, which is needed by many different departments, so that it can be used on a computer system that can meet the needs of these different departments. Implementation of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) at PT. XXX faces various obstacles due to differences in the systems used by the marketing, factory, and accounting departments which still work independently with their respective systems, causing data inconsistencies and hindering business process integration. Calculation of distributor turnover carried out by PT. XXX is an important part of evaluating company performance, but the system currently used still faces various challenges in terms of efficiency and integration between departments. PT. XXX has two types of distributors, namely distributors with cash payments and distributors with credit payments. Distributors with cash payments have a turnover calculated based on the money paid in advance before the goods are sent, while distributors with credit payments have a turnover calculated from the payment for goods that have been sent previously.

These differences in calculation methods often cause delays in turnover recapitulation, especially at the end of the year. The absence of an integrated system between departments results in the potential for duplication of turnover calculations and each department still relies on manual methods in recording transactions and calculating turnover, increasing the risk of errors and operational inefficiencies. External environmental factors that affect the effectiveness of information systems at PT. XXX are market dynamics and industry competition, companies must be able to respond to changes in customer demand quickly and accurately. Government regulations related to financial reporting and taxation systems also affect how data must be processed and reported transparently. The company faces challenges in adopting IT technology and infrastructure, where updating information systems requires large investments in software procurement, employee training, and ongoing system

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maintenance. There is resistance to change among employees and management. The implementation of the new system faces obstacles due to ingrained work habits and concerns about increasing work complexity.

Problem Identification

The miscalculation that occurred in the BEST OF THE BEST event shows that there are still processes that need improvement and simplification. The first step that the company must take is to map the business process to identify weak points that cause delays, data duplication, and the risk of manual errors. Identification is focused on several important aspects from the beginning of evaluating the process of collecting transaction data from distributors, both those using cash and credit payments. If this process is still done manually, the potential for data inconsistency will be high. Coordination between departments, especially between the sales team and the accounting department, must be strengthened to ensure better data synchronization. The company needs to identify redundant stages, such as double counting that can be simplified with automation. Integration is needed between information systems in each division so that all sales data is recorded in real-time without the need for separate recapitulation at the end of the period.

Solutions and Recommendations

In facing various obstacles that occur in calculating distributor turnover, PT. XXX needs to implement a number of solutions and recommendations designed to improve the accuracy, efficiency, and integration of the information system used. One of the main solutions is to replace the manual method that is still applied in several processes with an integrated automated system. This system must be able to record distributor transactions in real-time, both for distributors with cash and credit payments, thereby minimizing the risk of data errors and accelerating turnover recapitulation. After the parts that need improvement are identified, the next step is to develop an evaluation approach to support the development of a better and more integrated information system.

Using Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) is the answer for most companies because ERP integrates various core processes of the company, including finance, sales, inventory, production, and human resources, into one centralized platform. According to Chugh et al. (2017); Chofreh et al. (2018) ERP implementation affects the accounting process. Meanwhile, according to El Farmawi et al. (2019) through the ERP system, the accounting process can be well integrated so that it can produce accurate information. With a good ERP implementation, PT. XXX can unite the entire distributor turnover calculation process which was previously done manually and separately in various departments. ERP offers a solution to overcome problems such as delays in data recapitulation, duplication of information, and recording errors, because all data will be stored in one system with integrated and real-time access.

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Modularly, ERP software is usually divided into the main module, namely Operations, and supporting modules, namely Finance and Accounting and Human Resources:

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1. Operation Module

General Logistics, Sales and Distribution, Materials Management, Logistics Execution, Quality Management, Plant Maintenance, Customer Service, Production Planning and Control, Project System, Environment Management.

2. Financial & Accounting Module

General Accounting, Financial Accounting, Controlling, Investment Management, Treasury, Enterprise Controlling.

3. Human Resources Module

Personnel Management, Personnel Time Management, Payroll, Training and Event Management, Organizational Management, Travel Management

According to El Farmawi et al. (2019) ERP systems provide significant benefits in integrating business processes so that they become effective and efficient. ERP systems can automatically record every transaction that occurs, both from distributors who use cash and credit payment methods. Every payment received will be directly recorded in the financial module, while data related to the delivery of goods will be updated in the logistics module. Thus, there are no more differences in data between the sales, accounting, or logistics teams, so that potential errors due to differences in recording can be avoided. ERP is equipped with dashboard features and automatic reports that make it easy for management to monitor distributor turnover developments in real-time. According to Chugh et al. (2017) The benefits of ERP are felt directly by users or users through integrated accounting applications. Management who have direct access to this actual information can immediately find out the turnover achievements of each distributor and reduce the risk of errors when determining the winner in annual events such as BEST OF THE BEST. ERP can also provide automatic notifications regarding sales targets, payment due date reminders for credit distributors, and scheduled periodic reports.

ERP implementation at PT. XXX must be supported by a mature strategy to obtain optimal results. An important initial stage is the evaluation of system needs (needs assessment). This step aims to explore the needs of each related division, such as the marketing, factory, and accounting teams, in order to understand the features and functions needed in the new system so that the system developed will be able to handle turnover calculations automatically and in accordance with the situation in the field. Management must make a big decision with the next approach by conducting Business Process Reengineering (BPR), namely redesigning business processes to be more efficient and technology-based. Through BPR, companies can identify processes that do not provide added value and eliminate redundant stages. This includes simplifying the turnover calculation flow to be faster, more automatic, and minimize manual errors. In addition, PT. XXX needs to conduct a technical evaluation to ensure that the new system developed meets the required technical standards, such as data processing speed, integration capabilities between modules, and data security. A stable system that is able to record transactions in real time will help prevent errors in turnover calculations.

Coordination between departments must be improved, especially between the sales team and the accounting department, so that data synchronization runs more smoothly. Implementation of a digital-based dashboard that displays actual turnover data can also be a solution to provide fast and accurate access to information for all related parties, namely User Acceptance Testing (UAT) trials by end users, such as sales teams, factories, and accounting. The goal is to ensure that the system is easy to use, in accordance with operational needs, and is able to carry out its functions effectively. UAT also provides an opportunity for companies to obtain feedback from users before the system is officially launched. The last step is to carry out continuous improvement, because the development of information systems does not stop after implementation. This evaluation aims to ensure that the system remains relevant to changing business needs and can continue to be improved through performance monitoring and adjustments to new problems that may arise in the future.

El Farmawi et al. (2019) stated that companies that implement ERP can improve their innovation performance and performance quality which will have a direct impact on company performance, especially in increasing the accuracy of information between departments in the company, faster response to customers, and helping companies in decision making and good use of resources. Meanwhile, according to Karimi et al. (2017); Kirmizi et al. (2021) ERP implementation improves the quality of financial reports, reduces account closing time, reduces the time in presenting financial reports, and improves the decision-making process. With ERP, PT. XXX will have a system that not only speeds up the process of calculating turnover, but also improves overall operational accuracy and efficiency. Better integration between various divisions will create a smoother flow of information, thus supporting faster and data-driven decision-making.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis that has been conducted, there are several key findings that indicate the need for improvements in the distributor turnover calculation system at PT. XXX. One important finding is that the manual system that has been used so far still has significant weaknesses, such as the potential for data duplication, late recapitulation, and inconsistencies in calculation results between various departments, especially accounting and sales. This risks causing errors in turnover reporting, which can impact the smooth running of important company events, such as BEST OF THE BEST, where data accuracy is crucial. In addition, the inefficiency of the manual process also slows down the flow of information and makes it difficult to evaluate distributor performance in real time.

The implication of these findings for PT. XXX is that the company needs to immediately transform its information system to create better integration between departments. Implementation of an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system is the main recommendation, because ERP is able to integrate financial, sales, and logistics processes in one centralized platform. With an automated and real-time system, the company can reduce the risk of recording errors, increase the accuracy of turnover calculations, and accelerate the

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reporting and decision-making process. The development of an ERP system also has the potential to provide long-term impacts on the company's efficiency and productivity. ERP will not only make it easier to manage distributor turnover, but will also support PT. XXX in implementing a data-driven strategy, which allows the company to respond to market changes more quickly and precisely. To ensure successful implementation, the company needs to provide training for end users, as well as conduct continuous evaluation of system performance to keep it relevant to business needs.

REFERENCES

- Al-Zoubi, M. (2018). The role of technology, organization, and environment factors in enterprise resource planning implementation success in Jordan. *International Business Research*, 11(8), 48-65.
- Altamony, H., Al-Salti, Z., Gharaibeh, A., & Elyas, T. (2016). The relationship between change management strategy and successful enterprise resource planning (ERP) implementations: A theoretical perspective. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 7(4), 690-703.
- Chofreh, A. G., Goni, F. A., & Klemeš, J. J. (2018). Evaluation of a framework for sustainable Enterprise Resource Planning systems implementation. *Journal of cleaner production*, 190, 778-786.
- Chugh, R., Sharma, S. C., & Cabrera, A. (2017). Lessons learned from enterprise resource planning (ERP) implementations in an Australian company. *International Journal of Enterprise Information Systems (IJEIS)*, 13(3), 23-35.
- El Farmawi, W. (2019). Challenges affecting the implementation of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system: An analysis. *Journal of Systems Integration*, 10(3), 35-43.
- Febrianto *et al* (2022), Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and Implementation Suggestion to the Defense Industry: A Literature Review
- Karimi, J. (2017). Effects of Enterprise Resource Planning Implementation on Organizational Performance in the Transport Industry in Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, United States International University-Africa).
- Kirmizi, M., & Kocaoglu, B. (2021). The influencing factors of enterprise resource planning (ERP) readiness stage on enterprise resource planning project success: a project manager's perspective.

Saade, R. G., & Nijher, H. (2016). Critical success factors in enterprise resource planning implementation: A review of case studies. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*.

Shkurti, R., & Manoku, E. (2021). Factors of Success in Implementation of Enterprise Resource Planning Systems. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 18, 1084-1093.